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Synthesis and Antifungal Potency against *Aspergillus Niger* of Dimalononitriles derivatives of Cyclic Imides

Dr. Ravindra S. Dhivare^{1*}, Prof. Dr. Shankarsing S. Rajput²

¹Department of Chemistry, BSSPM's Arts, Commerce & Science College, Songir, Dhule, (MS), India

²Department of Chemistry, SVS's Dadasaheb Rawal College, Dondaicha, (MS), India

*Corresponding Author; Email: ravii_1978@rediffmail.com

ABSTRACT:

Heterocyclic imides greatly involves in the development of organic synthesis. To achieve the dimalononitriles were produced by active methylene group of dinitrile with cyclic imides via microwave solvent free method. Hence the spectrochemical properties and antifungal activities persisted to very active with greater potencies against *Aspergillus niger* fungal strain.

Keywords: *phenyl succinimide, phenyl glutarimide, malononitriles, Aspergillus niger*

1. INTRODUCTION:

Cyclic imides are familiarized with sulphur, oxygen and nitrogen heteroatom performs the vital role in the development of pharmaceutical, biochemical and agricultural extents. Heterocyclic imide shows good CNS and anti-depressive activities^[1] as well as cyclic imides^[2-3] like succinimides^[4-5], maleimides^[6], crotonimide-C^[7] of glutarimide^[8-10], itaconimide and isoindole 1, 3-dione^[11] showed the defensive antibacterial, antifungal, anti-proliferative^[12] anxiety inhibition and depression disorder^[13] activities. The synthesis of malononitrile groups furnished by Knoevenagel condensation reaction utilizing active methylene groups^[14] with substituted ketone, aldehydes, hetero-aromatic aldehydes or ketones or diones^[15] and indole derivatives. Mostly these are synthesized by aqueous media^[16], solvent one-pot^[18], KOH or NaOH^[19], ZnO^[20] and NH₄COOCH₃^[21] and tamarind juice catalyst^[22]. A number of malononitrile derivatives like cyanomethyl^[23], cyanoacetanilides^[24], benzopyranes^[25], cyanohexylidene malononitrile^[26], carbonitriles^[27] are simply prepared with active methylene group by conventional, grindstone method^[28], solvent free one or multicomponent and microwave assisted solvent free^[29] eco-friendly methods^[30].

2. EXPERIMENTAL METHOD:

All the compounds were synthesized in hours from the commercially purchased aniline, succinic anhydride, glutaric anhydride, vanillin, guanidine nitrate, hydrazine hydrate, dicyanomethane, acetyl chloride, neutral alumina, benzene and ethanol. Melting points are ensured and noted down by open-glass capillary and were uncorrected. IR spectra in KBr pellets were verified on

Shimadzu-FTIR: 8400S and ATR Brucker alpha FTIR spectrophotometer. ^1H NMR spectra were recorded by 200.13 MHz, 300.06 MHz, and 500.13 MHz using Brucker spectrophotometer. The reaction was monitored by TLC and performed using pre-coated silica-gel aluminium sheets.

2.1 General procedure for the preparation of 1-Phenyl Succinimide and Glutarimide:

The mixture of benzene and 1 mole succinic anhydride heated under reflux condition with constant stirring at 90-110 °C for 15 to 20 minutes till the clear solution formed. Then 1mole of aniline with 5ml benzene was slowly poured into the solution constantly stirred for 15 to 20 minutes turns homogeneous solution. Upon evaporation of benzene the 3-(1-phenyl) propanoic acid intermediate was obtained. Thereafter the mixture of 3-(1-phenyl) propanoic acid refluxed with 9mole acetyl chloride by constant stirring at the same time and temperature with the complete liberation of HCl gas. Then the mixture was cooled at room temperature which accomplished

the solid products 1-Phenyl Succinimide or 1-phenylpyrrolidine-2, 5-dione (**1a**) as shown in the **scheme -1**.

Scheme - 1: Synthesis of Phenylpyrrolidine-2, 5-dione (**1a**)

Same procedure was applied for the preparation of 1-Phenyl Glutarimide; glutaric anhydride (1mole) was refluxed with aniline (1mole) which form 3-(1-phenyl) butanoic acid and then refluxed with acetyl chloride (9mole) by constant stirring at the similar time and temperature, the 1-phenylpiperidine-2, 6-dione (**2a**) solid product was obtained in the **scheme -2**.

Scheme - 2: Synthesis of 1-phenylpiperidine-2, 6-dione (**2a**)

2.2 General procedure for the preparation of Dimalonitriles:

Malonitrile derivatives were synthesized by eco-friendly system. The mixture of 0.02mole of afforded 1-phenyl succinimides **1a** and 0.04mole of dicyanomethane in 2 gm of neutral Al_2O_3

irradiated by microwave in solvent free state on 640W power for 4-7 minutes accomplished the 2,2'-(1-phenylpyrrolidine-2,5-diylidene)dimalononitrile (9a) in the **scheme-3**.

Scheme - 3: Synthesis of 2,2'-(1-phenylpyrrolidine-2,5-diylidene)dimalononitrile (**3a**)

By working same method the 2,2'-(1-phenylpiperidine-2,6-diylidene)dimalononitrile (10a) derivative was synthesized by 0.02mole of afforded 1-phenyl glutarimides **2a** and 0.04mole of dicyanomethane in 2 gm of neutral Al_2O_3 by microwave supported solvent free state on same watt power and time as shown in the reaction **scheme-4**.

Scheme - 4: Synthesis of 2,2'-(1-phenylpiperidine-2,6-diylidene)dimalononitrile (**4a**)

2.3 Spectral Analysis:

2.3.1 1-phenylpyrrolidine-2, 5-dione(1a):

M.F.: $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_9\text{NO}_2$, C,H,N Observed: C, 68.15; H, 4.10; N, 8.50, FTIR (KBr): $>\text{C}=\text{O}$ (2-Peaks): 1708cm^{-1} and 1774cm^{-1} , cyclic $\text{CH}_2\text{-CH}_2$: 2937 cm^{-1} , cyclic imines 1291cm^{-1} , Ar (3-Peaks): 1457cm^{-1} , 1502cm^{-1} and 1595 cm^{-1} , $^1\text{H NMR}$ -(300.06 MHz, CDCl_3 , δ ppm) : 7.45-7.25 (m, 4H, Ar-H), 2.92 (s, 4H, imide)

2.3.2 1-phenylpiperidine-2, 6-dione(2a):

M.F.: $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{11}\text{NO}_2$, C,H,N Observed: C, 69.89; H, 5.46; N, 7.49, FTIR (ATR): $>\text{C}=\text{O}$ (2-Peaks): 1694cm^{-1} and 1770cm^{-1} , cyclic $\text{CH}_2\text{-CH}_2\text{-CH}_2$: 2971cm^{-1} , cyclic imines 1314cm^{-1} , Ar (3-Peaks):

1499 cm^{-1} , 1535 cm^{-1} and 1598 cm^{-1} , ^1H NMR-(300.06 MHz, CDCl_3 , δ ppm) :7.92-7.33 (d, 4H, Ar-H), 1.80 (m, 2H, $-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-$), 2.27 (t, 4H, imide)

2.3.3 2,2'-(1-phenylpyrrolidine-2,5-diylidene)dimalononitrile(3a)

M.F.: $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_9\text{N}_5$, C,H,N Observed: C, 71.34; H, 3.68; N, 25.98, FTIR (ATR): $-\text{Ca}''\text{N}$ (1-Peak): 2194 cm^{-1} , cyclic CH_2-CH_2 : 2918 cm^{-1} , cyclic imines 1379 cm^{-1} , Ar (3-Peaks): 1499 cm^{-1} , 1550 cm^{-1} and 1683 cm^{-1} , ^1H NMR-(300.06 MHz; $\text{DMSO}-d_6$; δ ppm): 2.76 (s, 4H, imide), 7.47-7.27 (m, 5H, Ar-H)

2.3.4 2,2'-(1-phenylpiperidine-2,6-diylidene)dimalononitrile(4a):

M.F.: $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_5$, C,H,N Observed: C, 71.84; H, 4.42; N, 24.78, FTIR (KBr): $-\text{Ca}''\text{N}$ (1-Peak): 2338 cm^{-1} , cyclic $\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2$: 2962 cm^{-1} , cyclic imines 1317 cm^{-1} , Ar (3-Peaks): 1501 cm^{-1} , 1541 cm^{-1} and 1602 cm^{-1} , ^1H NMR-(500.13 MHz; $\text{DMSO}-d_6$; δ ppm): 1.81 (m, 2H, imide), 2.28 (m, 4H, imide), 7.58-7.02 (m, 5H, Ar-H)

2.4 Antimicrobial Assay:

All the compounds were evaluated their antibacterial actions counter to *Aspergillus niger* (NICM-545) fungal strains at the concentration 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ per disc employing the paper disc diffusion method using DMSO solvent. Amphotericin-B was used as standard drug for antifungal activities. Zone of inhibition measured by digital vernier caliper in the figure-1and readings are noted.

Fig 1: Antifungal activities of cyclic imides and dimalononitriles

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

Cyclic imides **1a**, **2a** were prepared by conventional routes. Thereby eco-friendly microwave assisted solvent-free methods with neutral corundum (Al_2O_3) catalyst were practiced for further derivatives. The dimalononitriles **3a** and **4a** are prepared from cyclic imides. Physicochemical

data and spectral anal of all the synthesized compounds were verified. In the antibacterial frame of references, almost all the prepared derivatives are very active against *Aspergillus niger* fungal species.4. CONCLUSION:

At the end of the line, dimalonitriles derived from cyclic imides as starting components were synthesized by eco-friendly microwave system. These derivatives are very active against *Aspergillus niger* fungal strains. A few derivatives are highly potent against fungal species as compare with the standard drug. According to solvent free microwave route of the synthesis and antifungal efficacies, they might be used for different substituted heterocyclic entities.

REFERENCES

- [1] Bielenica A., Kossakowski J., Struga M., Dybala I., Loddo R., Ibba C., La Colla P., Synthesis and Biological Evaluation of New 3-Phenyl-1-[(4-arylpiperazin-1-yl)alkyl]- piperidine-2,6-diones, *Sci. Pharm.*, **2011**, 79, 225–238
- [2] Al-Azzawi M., and Hamd A. S., Synthesis, Characterization and Evaluation of Biological Activity of Novel Cyclic Imides Containing Heterocycles Based on 2,5-disubstituted-1,3,4-thiadiazoles, *Al-Anbar J. Vet. Sci.*, **2011**, 4(2), 152-164
- [3] Patil M. M. and Rajput S. S., Succinimides: Synthesis, Reaction and Biological activity, *International Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 2014; 6(11): 8-14
- [4] Al-Azzawi A. M. and Yaseen H. K., (2011), Synthesis and Characterization of New Phthalimides and Succinimides Substituted with 1,3,4-Oxadiazole Ring, *J. of University of Anbar for Pure Science*, **5(2)**, 1-12
- [5] Dhivare R. S. and Rajput S. S., Synthesis and antimicrobial activity of five membered cyclic imide derivatives of mono, di and tri substituted aromatic amines and naphthyl amine, *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, (2015), 4(6), 1650-1658
- [6] AL- Azzawi A. M. and Rahaan Mahdi S. A., (2013), Synthesis and Evaluation of Antimicrobial Activity of Several New Maleimides to Benzothiazole Moiety, *J. of Baghdad for Sci.*, **10(3)**, 658-672
- [7] Ndunda B., Langat M. K., Wanjohi J. M., Midiwo J. O. and Kerubo L. O., (2013), Alienusolin, a new 4 α -Deoxyphorbol Ester Derivative and Crotonimide C, a new Glutarimide Alkaloid from the Kenyan Croton Alienus, *Thieme, Planta Med.*, **79**, 1762-1766
- [8] Dhivare R. S. and Rajput S. S., Synthesis, Characterization and Antimicrobial Evolution of Six Membered Cyclic Imides, *International Journal of Chemistry and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 2015, 3(8): 1877–1880
- [9] Dhivare R. S., Rajput S. S. and Yadav R., Synthesis of new series of N-substituted phenyl succinimide and glutarimide derivatives for the study of their antifungal activity, *International Journal of Chemical Studies*, 2016, 4(1): 61-63
- [10] Rajput A.P. and Girase P.D., (2011), Synthesis, Characterization and Microbial Screening of Pyrazoline Derivatives of 2, 6-Dichloro-1-(N-Substituted Phenyl)-1, 4-Dihydropyridine-

- 3, 5-Dicarbalddehyde, *International Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, **3(4)**, 214-218.
- [11] Amin K. M., El-masry A. H., Mohamed N. A., Awad G. E. A. and Habib B. S., (2013), Synthesis, Characterization and Antimicrobial Activity of Some Novel Isoindole-1,3-Dione Derivatives, *Der Pharma Chemica*, **5(5)**, 97-108
- [12] Yunes J. A., Cardoso A. A., Yunes R. A., Correa R., Campos-Buzzi F. de and Filho V. C., (2008), Antiproliferative Effects of a Series of Cyclic Imides on Primary Endothelial Cells and a Leukemia Cell Line, *Verlag der Zeitschrift fur Naturforschung, Tubingen*, **63c**, 675-680
- [13] Matuszak N., Muccioli G. G., Labar J. and Lambert D. M., (2009), Synthesis and evaluation of N-substituted maleimide derivatives as selective monoglyceride lipase inhibitor, *Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, **52**, 7410-7420
- [14] Dhivare R. S. and Rajput S. S., Malononitrile: A Versatile Active Methylene Group, ISSN-2299-3843 in *International Letters of Chemistry, Physics and Astronomy* Vol. 57 (2015) 126-144
- [15] Gouda M. A. and Abu-Hashem A. A., (2012), An eco-friendly procedure for the efficient synthesis of arylidinemalononitriles and 4,4'-(arylmethylene)bis(3-methyl-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-5-ols) in aqueous media, *Green Chemistry Letters and Reviews*, **5(2)**: 203-209
- [16] Tamami B. and Fadavi A., (2006), A Polymeric Heterogeneous Catalyst Based on Polyacrylamide for Knoevenagel Reaction in Solvent Free and Aqueous Media, *Iranian Polymer Journal*, **15(4)**: 331-339
- [17] Fringuelli F., Piermatti O. and Pizzo F., (2004), One-Pot Synthesis of 7-Hydroxy-3-carboxycoumarin in Water, *Journal of Chemical Education*, **81(6)**: 874-876
- [18] Sheibani H. and Saljoogi A. S., (2012), A high-speed and eco-friendly catalytic system for Knoevenagel condensation of aldehydes with malononitrile and ethylcyanoacetate in aqueous media, *Heteroletters*, **2(4)**: 389-393
- [19] Basude M., Sunkara P. and Puppala V. S., (2013), ZnO catalyst for Knoevenagel condensation in aqueous medium at ambient temperature, *Journal of Chemical and Pharmaceutical Research*, **5(9)**: 46-50
- [20] Gupta R., Gupta M., Paul S. and Gupta R., (2009), Silica supported ammonium acetate: an efficient and recyclable heterogeneous catalyst for Knoevenagel condensation between aldehydes or ketones and active methylene group in liquid phase, *Bull. Korean Chem. Soc.*, **30(10)**: 2419-2421
- [21] Pal R., (2014), Visible light induced Knoevenagel condensation: A clean and efficient protocol using aqueous fruit extract of *tamarindus indica* as catalyst, *International Journal of Advanced Chemistry*, **2 (1)**: 27-33
- [22] Ammar H. B., Kaddachi M. T. and Kahn P. H., (2003), Conversion of malononitrile into 2-cyanomethyl compounds, *Phys. Chem. News*, **9**: 137-139
- [23] Fadda A. A., Bindock S., Rabie R. and Etman H. A., (2008), Cyanoacetamide derivatives as synthons in heterocyclic synthesis, *Turk J. Chem.*, **32**: 259-286

- [24] Hasaninejad A., Jafarpour N. and Mohammadnejad M., (2012), Synthesis of Benzo[b]pyrane Derivatives Using Supported Potassium Fluoride as an Efficient and Reusable Catalytic System, *E-Journal of Chemistry*, **9(4)**: 2000-2005
- [25] Dyachenko V. D. and Pugach Y. Y., (2013), Synthesis, molecular and crystal structure of 2-[2-(2-amino-3-cyano-4H-chromen-4-yl)-cyclohexylidene] malononitrile, *Russian Journal of General Chemistry*, **83(5)**: 979-982
- [26] Khalafy J., Rimaz M., Farajzadeh S. and Ezzati M., (2013), A Simple Three-component Synthesis of 3-Amino-5-arylpyridazine-4-carbonitriles, *S. Afr. J. Chem.*, **66**: 179-182
- [27] Pasha M. A., Manjula K. and Jayashankara V. P., (2010), Sodium carbonate: A versatile catalyst for Knoevenagel condensation, *Indian Journal of Chemistry*, **49(B)**: 1428-1431
- [28] Wang G. and Cheng G., (2004), Solvent free and aqueous Knoevenagel condensation of aromatic ketones with malononitrile, *ARKIVOC*, **ix**: 4-8
- [29] Dandia A., Singh R., Sachdeva H., Gupta R. and Paul S., (2003), Microwave promoted and improved thermal synthesis of Spiro-[indole-pyranobenzopyrans] and Spiro-[indole-pyranoimidazoles], *Journal of Chinese Chemical Society*, **50**: 273-278.
- [30] Dhivare R. S., Synthesis and biological study of pyrazoles, amino-pyrimidines and malononitriles derived from cyclic imides, Ph.D. Thesis, J.J.T. University, India, 2016.